

Challenges in Modeling and Forecasting Vehicle Miles Traveled

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Abstract

This research explores the vehicle miles traveled (VMT) by commercial trucks across six varied counties in California over the period from 2000 to 2020. The selected counties—Imperial, Los Angeles, Riverside, San Bernardino, San Diego, and San Francisco—encompass a wide range of California's demographic, economic, and geographic diversity. By analyzing a comprehensive dataset that includes demographic, economic, and pollution-related variables, this study aims to provide some of the challenges in modeling and forecasting the VMT and identify the key factors influencing commercial VMT. We utilized penalized regression models to examine the relationship among VMT and other demographic, economic, and pollution-related variables. The overall findings indicate that economic factors, particularly fuel consumption and vehicle population, have a substantial impact on total commercial VMT across the counties. Additionally, pollution variable like CO₂ contributes to these trends. These results highlight the importance of developing nuanced transportation and environmental policies, especially in response to economic fluctuations, to effectively and sustainably manage commercial truck VMT.

Key Words: Vehicle Miles Traveled (VMT), commercial transportation, penalized regression, pollution variables

1. Introduction

Vehicle Miles Traveled (VMT) is a fundamental metric in transportation analysis, providing essential insights into the usage and efficiency of transportation infrastructure. VMT measures the total distance traveled by all vehicles in specific regions, allowing policymakers and stakeholders in transportation to identify trends, challenges, and develop strategic responses (Federal Highway Administration, n.d.). Its significance is reflected in the ongoing scrutiny and analysis it has undergone, underscoring its critical role in assessing the evolving transportation landscape. The Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) projects a 22% increase in national VMT from 2019 to 2049 (Federal Highway Administration, 2020). This expected growth highlights the various factors driving VMT expansion, with significant contributions from different types of vehicles.

Light-duty vehicles account for the largest share of VMT, including personal vehicles used for commuting, errands, and leisure. Single-unit trucks, which include delivery vans, service vehicles, and small freight carriers, are essential for urban logistics and last-mile delivery. Combination trucks, such as tractor-trailers and heavy-duty freight vehicles, are critical for long-haul freight transportation, moving goods over long distances. According to FHWA projections, light-duty vehicle VMT will increase by 17% by 2049, driven by trends like population growth, urbanization, and economic expansion. In contrast, single-unit truck VMT is expected to surge by 101%, highlighting the growing importance of local and regional freight networks in supporting supply chains and commerce. Similarly, combination truck VMT is projected to grow by 57% during the same period, fueled by rising demand for goods movement and intermodal transportation solutions. This anticipated growth in commercial VMT emphasizes the need to examine the primary factors influencing transportation patterns and infrastructure use, as these have significant implications for urban mobility, environmental sustainability, and overall economic development. Effective transportation planning and policymaking are essential to address the challenges and opportunities presented by this projected increase in vehicular travel, ensuring that infrastructure investments

align with changing mobility needs, environmental goals, and societal priorities.

Understanding the drivers of commercial VMT growth is essential for developing sustainable and efficient transportation strategies. This paper aims to explore the key determinants of commercial VMT growth by analyzing factors such as economic trends, demographic changes, and pollution-related variables. Various studies have sought to identify factors that affect VMT. For example, Brownstone and Golob (2009) investigated the relationship between residential density, vehicle usage, and energy consumption, finding that higher residential density is associated with reduced vehicle usage and lower energy consumption, which suggests that urban planning policies can promote sustainable transportation practices. McMullen and Eckstein (2012) explored the relationship between VMT and economic activity in the United States, challenging the common belief that economic growth leads to increased VMT. Their study found that economic activity often drives VMT, and that external shocks to VMT are unlikely to harm national GDP, though the relationship varies across different stages of the business cycle and is not significant for urban areas. Woldeamanuel and Kent (2014) identified that income, fuel prices, vehicle ownership, and land use significantly affect per capita VMT trends in California. Newmark et al. (2015) examined the link between income, location efficiency, and VMT, focusing on affordable housing as a strategy to mitigate climate change. They suggest that affordable housing located in transit-rich areas can reduce VMT, indicating that housing policies can help address climate change by reducing transportation-related emissions. Loder, Tanner, and Axhausen (2017) analyzed the impact of local work and residential balance on VMT using detailed GPS data, finding that balanced work and residential locations can significantly lower VMT, underscoring the importance of spatial planning in reducing transportation-related environmental impacts.

Beyond investigating the relationship between commercial VMT and other factors, this paper also focuses on forecasting commercial VMT. Kumapley and Fricker (1996) highlighted the importance of VMT estimates in transportation planning, emphasizing the need for objective comparisons of different estimation methods. Their review of methods used by the Indiana Department of Transportation (INDOT) showed that traffic count-based estimates were generally 10 to 20 percent higher than estimates from a non-traffic-data cross-classification model. Polzin et al. (2004) projected future VMT in the United States using predictive models based on transportation data and trends, revealing an upward trend in VMT and emphasizing the need for infrastructure planning and transportation policy development to manage growing travel demand. Williams et al. (2016) explored various methodologies for estimating and forecasting VMT, including statistical modeling, travel demand models, and data-driven approaches, underscoring the need for tailored methods to improve VMT prediction accuracy for effective transportation planning and policy decisions.

The structure of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 details the data and methodology, including data sources, input-output variables, and their statistical summaries. It also discusses the modeling approach, starting with multiple linear regression and addressing any limitations encountered. Section 3 presents the results from LASSO regression, ridge regression, and elastic net regression, along with an evaluation of their forecasting capabilities. Finally, Section 4 offers concluding remarks.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1 Data and Data Collection

This study examines six diverse California counties: Imperial, Los Angeles, Riverside, San Bernardino, San Diego, and San Francisco, each with distinct demographics, landscapes, and socioeconomic characteristics. These counties represent the state's geographical and cultural diversity, from Los Angeles' urban sprawl to San Diego's coastal beauty and Imperial's agricultural heartland. Analyzing these counties together helps us understand the relationships among VMT, demographics, economics, and pollution.

County Characteristics:

1. **Imperial County:** Agricultural focus, desert climate, low population density.

2. **Los Angeles County:** Most populous U.S. county, diverse economy, varied geography.
3. **Riverside County:** Rapidly growing, desert landscape, urban areas like Palm Springs.
4. **San Bernardino County:** Largest by area, diverse geography, economic diversity.
5. **San Diego County:** Coastal, mild climate, strong military and biotechnology presence.
6. **San Francisco County:** Compact, high cost of living, technological and cultural hub.

The dataset, covering 2000-2020, is sourced from [FRED](#) and the [California Air Resources Board](#). It includes demographics, economic indicators, and pollution variables, offering a comprehensive view of the interactions between these factors and VMT across the counties. Table 1 below lists the variable names and provides the descriptions.

Table 1: Variable names and their descriptions.

VARIABLES	DESCRIPTIONS
MEDIAN INCOME	Median household income (in Dollars)
UNEMPLOYMENT	Unemployment rate (in %)
EMPLOYED	Employed Per
GDP	County Gross Domestic Product (in Dollars)
HOUSE PRICE INDEX	All-Transaction House Price Index
SNAP	Supplemental Nutrition Assistance Program Benefit Recipients
POVERTY	Estimate of People of All Ages in Poverty
POPULATION	Resident Population (in 1,000)
PREMATURE	Age-Adjusted Premature Death Rate (Rate per 100,00)
VEHICLE POPULATION	County Vehicle Populations
TRIPS	Number of Trips
NOX	Nitrogen Oxides
PM2.5	Particulate matter 2.5 with diameter 2.5 microns or less
PM10	Particulate matter 10 with diameter 10 microns or less
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
N2O	Nitrous Oxide
CO	Carbon Monoxide
SOX	Sulfur Dioxide
TOTAL VMT	Total Vehicle Miles Traveled

Figure 1 shows the trends in Total Vehicle Miles Traveled (VMT) across various regions from 2000 to 2019. The y-axis represents the Total VMT, while the x-axis shows the years. The graph indicates a general trend of increasing VMT from 2000 to a peak around 2005-2007, followed by a decline that reaches a low around 2012. After this period, VMT generally increases again, with another peak around 2016-2018 before a slight decline toward 2019. Different regions show similar patterns, though some fluctuations and variations are unique to specific regions, such as a more pronounced peak in San Francisco around 2016.

Figure 1: Time series plots of total VMT for the counties.

2.2 Methodology

Linear regression, a foundational data analysis method, models the relationship between independent variables (x) and a dependent variable (y) using the equation:

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik} + \epsilon_i$$

Here, y is the outcome variable, β_0 is the intercept, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k$ are the coefficients representing the effect of each input variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k , and ϵ is the error term. The ordinary least squares (OLS) method is typically used to estimate these parameters by minimizing the sum of squared residuals. However, when the number of observations (n) is smaller than the number of variables (k), OLS struggles due to matrix inversion issues.

To overcome this, we introduce a penalty term into the objective function:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n [y_i - (\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik})]^2 + \left[\alpha \sum_{j=1}^k |\beta_j| + (1 - \alpha) \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j^2 \right].$$

Where λ is the regularization parameter. LASSO regression ($\alpha=1$) focuses on feature selection by shrinking some coefficients to zero, while Ridge regression ($\alpha=0$) addresses multicollinearity. Elastic net regression, with $0 < \alpha < 1$, combines both methods. Our analysis uses LASSO ($\alpha=1$), ridge ($\alpha=0$), and elastic net ($\alpha = 0.5$) to enhance model interpretability and robustness.

The dependent variable in our study is total commercial VMT, with other variables serving as predictors. We also include a lagged total VMT variable to explore temporal dependencies, providing insights into how past VMT influences current patterns.

3. Analyses and Results

Before conducting the LASSO, ridge, and elastic net regressions, all variables were standardized using the z-score method to ensure comparability across variables. This standardization allows us to evaluate the relative importance of each predictor in influencing total commercial VMT.

LASSO regression adds a penalty to the regression model that forces some coefficients to zero, effectively performing variable selection. This method helps identify the most influential predictors while reducing overfitting. Ridge regression also adds a penalty to the regression model that shrinks the coefficients but does not force them to zero. This method helps manage multicollinearity and

reduces overfitting by keeping all predictors in the model but controlling their influence. The regularization term in ridge regression ensures that the model remains stable and less sensitive to minor variations in the data. Elastic net regression combines LASSO and ridge regression penalties to handle scenarios with many correlated features. This approach allows for a more comprehensive variable selection while managing multicollinearity.

Table 2 provides the magnitudes of the coefficients of the variables. For LASSO, all values are zero across all variables and counties. For ridge, coefficients also vary and include both positive and negative values, indicating adjustments for multicollinearity; the values range, for example, from -0.07 to 0.15. For elastic net, values vary by variable and county, indicating coefficients assigned by the model; for instance, the values for Population Vehicle range from 0 to 0.05.

Table 2: A table showing the coefficients of the variables from each model for each county.

Variable\County	LASSO						Ridge						ElasticNet					
	Imperial	LA	Riverside	SB	SD	SF	Imperial	LA	Riverside	SB	SD	SF	Imperial	LA	Riverside	SB	SD	SF
Population.Vehicle	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.09	0.13	0.12	0.11	0.09	0.04	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.04	0	0
Trips	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.09	0.15	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.08	0.07	0.1	0	0.04	0.03	0
NOx_TOTEX	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0.01	0.01	0	-0.01	-0.04	0	0	0	0	0	0
PM2.5_TOTEX	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.03	-0.07	0	0	0	0	0	0
PM10_TOTEX	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.03	-0.07	0	0	0	0	0	0
CO2_TOTEX	0.67	0.41	0.68	0.65	0.46	0	0.23	0.21	0.21	0.2	0.22	0.3	0.24	0.22	0.29	0.28	0.24	0.29
N2O_TOTEX	0.02	0.12	0	0	0.25	0	0.22	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.16	0.2	0.2	0.07	0.11	0.24	0.05
CO_TOTEX	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0.01	0.02	0	-0.02	0	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0
SOx_TOTEX	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0.04	0.06	0.01	0.03	0.09	0.07	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fuel.Consumption	0	0.14	0.01	0	0	0.78	0.23	0.22	0.21	0.2	0.23	0.35	0.23	0.23	0.3	0.28	0.23	0.41
Population.County	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.04	-0.01	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0
MedIncIncome	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0.07	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.13	0	0	0	0	0	0.18
Unemployment	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0.06	0.01	-0.04	-0.03	-0.01	0.02	0	0	0	0	0	-0.03
Employed	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.02	0.09	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.17	0	0.03	0	0	0.02	0.05
GDP.All	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.03	0.04	0.02	-0.01	0.03	0.12	0	0	0	0	0	0.16
Poverty	0	-0.24	0	0	0	0	-0.04	-0.07	-0.07	-0.06	-0.06	-0.08	0	-0.16	0	0	0	-0.08
SNAP	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0.01	-0.04	-0.02	-0.01	-0.07	-0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0
Premature	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0.14	0.02	-0.11	-0.1	-0.08	-0.05	-0.04	0	-0.04	-0.02	0	0
HousePriceIndex	0	0	0	0.05	0	0.14	0.06	-0.01	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.04	0	0.06	0.04	0	0.07
TotalVMT.1	0.11	0	0.12	0.13	0.11	0	0.08	0.03	0.08	0.08	0.07	0	0.1	0.04	0.16	0.14	0.15	0.03

Figure 2: A comparison of the models using Mean Square Error (MSE).

Figure 2 illustrates the shows the Mean Squared Error (MSE) comparison among LASSO, Ridge, and elastic net models for different counties. LASSO consistently has the highest MSE values across all counties, indicating poorer performance compared to the other models. Elastic net shows a moderate performance, with MSE values lower than LASSO but higher than Ridge in some cases. Ridge generally has the lowest MSE values across most counties, suggesting it is the best-performing model among the three for this dataset. This visualization clearly illustrates the relative performance differences among the models, with Ridge typically providing the best results in terms of lower MSE.

4. Conclusion

This study analyzed six diverse California counties—Imperial, Los Angeles, Riverside, San Bernardino, San Diego, and San Francisco—each with unique demographics, landscapes, and socioeconomic characteristics. The goal was to capture the multifaceted nature of these communities by examining data from 2000 to 2020, focusing on three main categories: Demographics, Economics, and Pollution. The primary outcome variable is total commercial vehicle miles traveled (VMT), which represents the total distance traveled by commercial trucks for transportation purposes.

Linear regression, along with LASSO and elastic net regression, were employed to explore the relationships between various factors and total commercial VMT across the counties. LASSO and elastic net regressions were particularly useful for feature selection and regularization in datasets with numerous variables. The analysis identified key predictors of total commercial VMT, including vehicle population, fuel consumption, CO₂ and PM_{2.5} pollution, median income, employment, and poverty.

Correlation plots highlighted the relationships between input variables and total VMT, showing positive correlations with the number of trips, CO₂ and N₂O emissions, and fuel consumption, while unemployment and poverty showed negative correlations. Data visualizations revealed total VMT trends from 2000 to 2020, including a notable decline in the early 2010s, likely influenced by the 2008 financial crisis and fluctuating fuel prices.

In summary, this study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing total commercial VMT in these six California counties over two decades. Key findings include the significant impact of vehicle population and fuel consumption on VMT, the relevance of CO₂ and PM_{2.5} pollution variables, and the role of economic factors such as median income and employment in shaping transportation patterns. The study also underscores the sensitivity of commercial transportation to economic downturns, as evidenced during the post-2008 financial crisis period. These findings can guide policymakers, urban planners, and transportation authorities in developing targeted strategies to manage and optimize commercial transportation, improve air quality, and address socioeconomic disparities, thereby fostering sustainable and efficient transportation systems across California.

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Appendix

Figure 3: Heatmap correlation coefficients of the variables.

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